

Design and Emotion: Systemic led Relations between Subjects and Designed Objects

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Abstract

Within the polysystemic field of Design, the question of "Emotions" leads to the relation between Subject and Object. In order to show how, I will suggest that, both at the level of the production and at the level of the reception of designed Objects, Emotions in the field of design are linked to the rules of the Systems involved, the positioning of the Subjects towards the Systems and "Object a", a Lacanian borrowed concept. Emotions, therefore, will be presented as relying on the systemic led relations between Subjects and designed Objects as these include an embedded "Object a".

Keywords: design, polysystemic field, System, Subject, Object, Object a, Consumer, Designer

I. Introduction

"Emotions" towards designed objects created/produced by designers in the field of design, can be grasped in terms of "Object a". A vivid concept of Lacanian psychoanalysis, "Object a" will contribute to discuss designers and users-consumers' Emotions towards objects or projects. I will therefore begin with a few theoretical premises, proceed with the links between Design, Systems, and Emotions, introduce Shay Barkan's design work and close with conclusions.

II. Theoretical premises

1. "Positive Emotions" as opposed to "non positive Emotions"

Within the field of psychoanalysis, "Emotions" is **not** a commonly used term. However, based on their radical opposition, psychoanalytic concepts such as "Principle of Pleasure" and "Principle of Reality" create a conceptual environment within which the notion of "Emotions" can be transferred and translated.

"Pleasure" and "Principle of Pleasure" standing in opposition to "Reality" and "Principle of Reality", we will link the two radically opposed poles with 2 groups of emotions: "positive Emotions" as opposed to "non positive Emotions". Love versus Hate, Pleasure versus Displeasure, Content versus Discontent, Attraction versus Repulsion.

The relation between positive-non positive Emotions and Objects emphasizes what Lacan refers to as "Relation d'Objet" ("Object Relation") (Lacan,(1956-57)1994) thus indicating that "Objects" can be the cause of Emotions, motivate pleasure, joy and eventually provoke reluctance.

The mutual relation between Emotions and Objects and their reciprocal influence raise questions such as: "What is an "Object?" "What does "Object" refer to?" "What do we refer to as "Object"?" or: "What do we refer to when we say "Object"?"

2. "Object" as opposed to "Subject"

To these questions we will first answer that Lacanian psychoanalysis differentiates between two concepts: the concept of "Object" and the concept of "Subject". "Subject" is a concept used to define humans as these are led by their "Speech" and their "Desire", two of the basic fundamental concepts for the definition of the "Subject".

(Lacan,(1966)1977) "Object" is mainly a linguistic signifier independent of Desire and Speech or which Desire and Speech do not refer to. It can also be whatever a Subject "sees" as such, and/or whatever a Subject relates to as such.

3. Language ["Langue"] as opposed to Speech ["Parole"].

As we know from Ferdinand de Saussure's Modern Linguistics (Saussure,(1916)1976), "Speech" – *Parole* - is not "Language" – *Langue*- though it is linked to Language. The linguist's – Saussure- interest goes to Language, which he defines as a **system** of signs (Saussure,(1916)1976). The psychoanalyst's interest goes to Speech that, says Lacan ((1966)1977), depends on the position the Subject takes in relation to the System. Lacan will relate to the System as "A" – "Le Grand Autre" (Lacan,(1956-57)1977).

4. "Object a"

The Subject's distancing itself from the System - that is to say, from all the apparatus of already determined, fixed and established signs - is a process which involves a Subject's desire as defined by what Lacanian psychoanalysis calls "**Object a**" ("*Objet petit a*") (Lacan,(1956-57)1977). According to Lacanian psychoanalysis, "Object a" is the Object which motivates the Subject's desire, brings it about and enlightens it. "Object a" is also the Object which helps define the Subject's desire in terms of content and meaning. Thus, when "Object a" is missing, the Subject's desire - "the Desire of the Subject"- not only will **not** come into light, but will remain empty of (its) content and meaning.

In Lacanian psychoanalysis, "Object a" is defined as either a **signifier** - "*un signifiant*"- (Lacan,(1956-57)1977), or **no thing** of the order of Language. In both cases, "Object a" **cannot be a sign** for it can have no prerequisite defined signified.

5. "Object a" and material objects

Although referred to as "Object", "Object a" has no materiality and therefore is **not** a material object. Nevertheless, "Object a" is engraved in the materiality of designed material objects and as such, can be captured in and through the design of material objects. It is by that token that the Subject's desire will be grasped thus showing that "Object a" not only reflects the Subject's desire but also arouses the Subject's emotions. Thus, when defined as Subjects, Designers and Users-Consumers find themselves brought together by "Object a".

6. Design as a polysystemic field

No doubt then, that there is a need to relate to "Object a" in the context of design. For that purpose, we will first define "design" as a polysystemic heterogeneous field (Itamar Even Zohar, 1970-1990) based on more than one system and deal with Emotions in terms of "poly-systemic relations" or/and "systemic relations". This approach will allow us to explore Emotions in terms of the relations between "Object a", Designers, Users-Consumers and designed material objects, and define Emotions as "systemic led responses" within each system of the "poly-systemic" environment.

"Emotions" will refer to Designers as well as to Users-Consumers not only because both are Subjects but also because both are System related. In any case, Emotions will imply the Subject's relations to the systems, thus leading to notions such as "position" and "positioning" (Lacan, (1956-57) 1994) and to the idea that Emotions are the effects of the Subject's positioning and the Subject's position in relation to the systems involved. Thus, positioning, position and systemic relations will help uncover not only "Object a" itself but the way "Object a" helps motivates-the designer and his/her work of design, stands within the materiality of the designer's designed object and influences Users-Consumers' emotions.

III. "Object a", System and design polysystemic field

Since we have defined the field of design as a polysystemic field, we will thereon introduce three different systems. To the first system, we will relate as "**Language-System**" and define designers' positioning in terms of designer's relation to linguistic

signs. To the second system we will relate as "**Culture-System**" and define designer's positioning in terms of designer's relation to cultural signs. As for the third system, we will name it "**Subject-System**" and define designer's positioning in terms of designer's relation both to linguistic signs, cultural signs and designer's "Object a".

III.1 Language-System

The Language System- System 1– is based on the concept of "sign" as defined by Ferdinand de Saussure ((1916)1976) in the field of linguistics, and implies two secondary subordinated concepts: the signifier and the signified.

In that system, Objects are signs. Objects-signs have a defined identity, which is supposed to be known by the Speakers of the Language. Thus, in that context, the equation "a chair is a chair" becomes true for all the Language's Speakers.

The different Objects-signs or types of Objects-signs designed within the frame of System 1 have to adhere to the definitions of the linguistic signs, as contemporary dictionaries state these. Designed Objects-signs, therefore, cannot but fit the basic definition of the linguistic sign both through their formal representation ("signifier" as "image") (Saussure,(1916)1976) and through their referent, content and meaning (the "signified" as "concept") (Saussure, (1916)1976). Thus, in System 1, designers are compelled to submit their design practice and its results, to the identity of the linguistic signs. Based on a sign's signified and signifier, designed Objects-signs will accept **only** well-known forms of representation by which their identity will be well defined. As such, designed Objects-signs will easily be identified by those who see them and recognize them as (linguistic) signs.

Within the frame of a Language design systemic approach, designed Objects-signs will be performed in terms of well-known forms and well-known structures. Thus, by bounding their work to the limits defined by the signs of Language, from which they will not depart, designers who design within that frame will be required to **re-produce** well known forms and well known structures.

Designing in System 1, implies submitting to the Law – (of) Language. Hence, designing relies not only on shared *collective* signs - including shared *collective* forms of representation, but on a *collective* ability to identify easy-to-identify designed Objects-signs. It is in that context that "Object a" takes the form of “the collective” – **a signifier** which reflects *collective* signs, *collective* forms of representation, and *collective* designed Objects-signs. Defining designer's desire to design in terms of "commitment" to what can be defined as “a linguistic community”, the "collective" signifier adds socio-political ideological values to the practice of design. Based on concepts such as "function", "functionality", "use", "technical" and "technological" rather than "aesthetic" "collective" is shared by both designers and consumers in whom it arouses positive emotional responses. (1)

III.2 Culture-System

To the second system – System 2 -, we will refer as **Culture-System**. Based on the concept of “sign”, Culture-System in the field of design follows Barthes' idea that linguistic signs have an added / additional value when placed within the realm of a culture. (Mythologies (1956)1970)

Most nowadays developed western societies consider that in the field of design, aesthetic is an additional value. Relying on aesthetic parameters, concepts such as "Line" and "Look" indeed reflect the importance of aesthetic values as these are added to Objects-signs.

Culture-System major aesthetic categories are- materials, colors, transparencies, types of lines which designers use to encode designed Objects-signs in order to transform them into "Object-products".

Within a given Culture, aesthetic parameters are quite clear cut and well defined. They therefore form a common collective data, which *guides* designers and Consumers as well. Aesthetic parameters guide designers as these reproduce them in the process of designing of Objects-products thus showing why System 2 designers should expand their knowledge of aesthetic cultural categories. They also guide Consumers when these apprehend them as a value added to the Object-product, for in System 2, "Aesthetics" is the Law. It acts as a constraint both on the design/ing of Objects-products and on the

reactions to designed Objects-products. Thus, when identified as the system led "Object a", "Aesthetics" is what designers and Consumers respond to. Given that "Aesthetics" is "Object a" which affects both designers and Consumers, who both embrace aesthetic cultural parameters as added values to Objects-products, response to "Aesthetics" cannot be but a positive emotional one.

III.3 Subject System

I will refer to the third system – System 3 – as "**Subject System**" or as "The System of the Subject". "Subject" is a term I have borrowed from Lacanian psychoanalysis to define a human being –whose *identity* relies on two basic but not exclusive parameters: "Speech" and "Desire". Although defined as "a human being", Lacan refers to the "Subject" as "it", with no regards to gender or/and gendered linguistic devices.

With concepts such as "Speech" and "Desire", designers become "Designers-Subjects". Led by their Desire, Designers-Subjects are designers whose positioning can be defined in both negative and positive terms; for on one hand, Designers-Subjects' positioning rests on their desire to keep themselves aloof from the Language System and from the Cultural System which rely on rules they do not wish to identify with. And on the other hand, Designers-Subjects' positioning rests on their desire to design according to their own rules.

Designing according to one's own rules and not according to the rules of the Systems, means designing according to one's Object of Desire which, in Lacanian terms, is "Object a". In System 3, "Object a", referring to what Lacan calls "the gaze", is the Object which Designers-Subjects "see" in front of their "eyes". (Lacan:(1966)1977) This "Object a" **necessarily** introduces new visual forms of representation for, **necessarily** reflecting Designers- Subjects' positioning towards linguistic and cultural signs, it can be neither a linguistic sign nor a cultural sign. It has to be something else.

Thus, in System 3, "Object a" can be either a signifier or not.

As a signifier, it will **necessarily** lead the designer to transform a linguistic signifier from given forms of representation into new ones. In that case, designers' work will **necessarily** rely on at least three processes by the means of which designers will propose new lines, forms, or/and structures to the signifier. These three processes are:

- Designer's **remodeling of** well-known forms of representation into new or not yet known forms of representation.
- Designer's **transformation of** well-known canonical forms of representation of signs.
- Designer's **creation** of new forms of representation.

As a non-signifier, "Object a" will have no reference either to a linguistic sign or to a cultural sign. It will appear as stamped, carved or engraved within the materiality of new forms of representation of newly designed material objects as these have been seen by the designer.

However, in System 3, material Objects will require procedures of identification. Not only in order to help bring the Designers-Subjects' "Object a" out of the designed material objects either as a signifier or as a non-signifier, but also in order to give these material Objects their identity, for by introducing new innovatory forms of representation, System 3 designers **necessarily** inaugurate new material Objects. Given that material Objects identification allows material Objects recognition and that recognition gives material Objects a place on the market, we will understand the importance of such identification procedures.

IV. The case of Shay Barkan

[Insert = photographs of SBarkan's work]

It is in the context of System 3 that I wish to present the work of Shay Barkan. Born in Israel in 1956, Shay Barkan studied Art for one year and Industrial Design for 4 years, at Betzalel Academy of Art and Design in Jerusalem. His work presents two basic fundamental characteristics: its formal aspect and its relation to metal.

Barkan's choice of "metal" as a basic signifier and a basic material is neither without reason nor without meaning. With what Lacan calls the "Imaginary" ((1966)1977), Barkan's choice is linked to the meanings he grants to "metal" in terms of *strength*,

hardness, stiffness and violence. With what Lacan calls “the Symbolic” ((1966)1977), Barkan's choice is linked to the meanings he grants to "metal" in terms of "*Phallic Patriarchy*". Barkan's design work can therefore be understood as the designer's way/ means to bend the Law - the Law of the Father - which he sees as *violent* and *powerful*.

Opposed to the rules of Power, [ideologically] opposed to the Power of the rules and opposed to all the systems which on behalf of their Power, impose their Law on the Subject, Barkan, not only "de-structures" and "de- constructs" the common well known shared forms of representation of signs but also creates forms of representation of his own. Thus, although he uses basic linguistic signifiers such as "vase", "lamp" and "chair", Barkan the Designer-Subject denies the signifiers their commonly accepted formal identity. Replacing the signifiers' well known forms of representation by new ones, Barkan creates new formal identities. For, when he bends, folds, crumples and crushes "metal", not only does he fight against (its) *strength, hardness* and *stiffness*, but on that basis, he also creates metal-Objects in which fluid lines and forms introduce new identities.

It is the violence of his opposition to the rules and to the Law, his refusal of the Law - of the Father, and his desire of **no Law** or of the Law of the Subject, - the **other Law**, that leads Barkan to an alternative aesthetics representation. Barkan's alternative aesthetics representation is therefore the effect of his position towards the Law. Reflecting the designer's positioning, "Object a" is embedded in his approach to design, designing and Objects. It appears within Barkan's designed objects. For, being designed "as- if- by- accident" or "as-if-with-no-design", these rely on the *fluidity* of their lines and the *smoothness* of their structures, displaying *spontaneity, openness and an airiness* which reveal Barkan's desire of/for *freedom*.

In the field of design, Barkan cannot realize his work of design but within System 3. For, System 3 alone allows designers who cannot conceive designing according to pre-imposed rules, to design – out of their limits.

V. What does "Object a" have to do with Consumer's Emotions?

Consumers, buyers - and all those supporters or fans - who will express their interest in Shay Barkan's designed objects, will not only show their understanding of the designer's work and aesthetics, but will also reveal how they identify with his "Object a". For, as they detect, recognize and feel moved by the **traces** it leaves in the materiality of the material designed metal objects, "supporters" respond to "Object a" through positive Emotions. Traces therefore, reflect "Object a" and behave as transitional agents. It is on their behalf that Designers and Consumers meet. Thus, while Consumer's supportive recognition of Barkan's design work shows that Consumers identify with his "Object a", it also shows that Consumer's and Designer's share a common "Object a". For, it is because they are driven by a similar "Object a" to the Designer's, that Consumers express positive Emotions towards designer's subversive metal-Objects. Eventually, they will even express their desire to purchase them.

VI. Conclusion

Are Emotions an individual's reactions to material objects? My answer to this question is that although being an individual's reactions, Emotions rely on the Systems of the polysystemic field of Design. In that context, I have tried to show that within each System of the polysystemic field, Emotions are the effect of both Designers' and Consumers' relations to "Object a" as this is linked to both the rules of the Systems and the positioning of the Subjects towards the Systems. In fact, the more the Subject identifies with the Systems of Language and Culture, the closer the Subject's "Object a" is to the (Ideal) Object of the Systems. The less the Subject identifies with the Systems of Language and Culture, the further the Subject's "Object a" is to the (Ideal) Object of the Systems. Given that most Subjects identify with the Systems of Language and Culture, we will understand why most designed products are mass-produced. Nevertheless, since few Subjects stand out of the two main Systems, one-off Objects in the field of design are not only possible but acceptable. In other words, Objects produced within the System of the Subject are an integral part of the polysystemic field of Design and therefore do not belong to any other field.

*(1) see: Boris Arvatov's "Everyday life and the Culture of the Thing" (1925)1997
,translation Kristina Kaier.*

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